

Bank Restructuring in Vietnam

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Abstract:

Bank restructuring is an important program for emerging countries to build a prudential financial system. Evaluating the association between restructuring program and bank efficiency is important to achieve a successful implementation of government policy.

Key words: Restructuring, Bank efficiency

1. Introduction

During mid-1990s, a large number of Vietnamese banks and financial institutions were established. The financial system reformed, therefore, it was necessary to stimulate the domestic investment effectively by supplying services and environment for foreign and domestic entities which were operating. There was a significant increase in bank credit growth of from 18% of GDP in 1991 to about 21% in 1997 (source GSO 1998)¹.

In Vietnam, the gross domestic saving rate increased significantly from 2.9% in 1990 to 16.2% in 1992 and reached 18.0% in 1997 (source GSO 1998). It was a result of the significant increase in the number of private banks, foreign, and mixed ownership marked improvement in financial services. However, when compared to China and other emerging economies, such as Malaysia and Thailand (Harvie and Hoa, 1997), Vietnamese's growth was lower. Most of new banks entering the Vietnam banking system were small and remained dominated by the SOCBs². Consequently, the Vietnam banking system remained lacking both competitiveness and innovation; hence, Vietnam was considered to be an "under-banked country".

It is interesting to note that since the expansion in 2000, the Vietnamese economy has faced many problems such as high percentage of non-performing, increasing bad debt to 8.6% in 2012 (SBV, 2012)³ and cross ownership between banks. Banking crisis, which was stem from global financial crisis and weak domestic economy led to the default of a lot of banks such as De Nhat bank, Tin Nghia bank and Habu bank. As a result, the government launched bank-bailout policies to restructure banks and improve the efficiency.

Since 2000, Vietnamese government has started the privatization of State Commercial Banks to help them reach regional and international standards. However, restructuring activities were not strongly conducted until 2005. During the period from 2007 to 2008, two state commercial banks, Vietcom and Vietinbank, performed equitization. After the equitized process, their growth rates increased with high level of some key financial indicators and with the lowest NPL ratio over the entire system. Moreover, they have played an important role in leading the financial market after the equitization. Currently, Vietcom and Vietin are two banks with the largest charter capital and their total assets have risen by several times compared to 2005.

¹ General statistics office of Vietnam report 1998

<https://www.gso.gov.vn/default.aspx?tabid=715>

² State own commercial banks 1993

³ State Bank of Vietnam annual report 2012

http://www.sbv.gov.vn/portal/faces/en/enpages/public/areports?_afLoop=9020155200469715&_afWindowMode=0&_afWindowId=adyam513z_901

Additionally, the transformation from rural commercial banks to urban ones conformed to the market economy during the period of 2005-2007. The “upgrade” in the banking system was an extremely important step. It not only raised charter capital of commercial banks, but also changed the management mechanism of each bank in accordance with the international trend.

Over the period from 2011 to 2013, weak banks were urged to perform restructuring which was supported and monitored by the government and State Bank. During this phase, there were different forms of restructuring including recapitalization, M&A, privatization, assistance from State bank, and VAMC establishment.

In recent years, M&A has been the main method to restructure banks in Vietnam with nine transactions so far. All banks were restructured by transforming the operation model and increasing capital. In certain circumstances, solving the weaknesses of the banking system was top priority, and the establishment of an asset management company was also inevitable.

2. Bank restructuring in Vietnam

a. The change of bank ownership

In the early 2000s, Vietnamese government had a privatization plan for state commercial banks to put Vietnam's banking and financial sector on a par with other countries in the region.

During the period of 2003-2007, all the first rural commercial banks were transformed into urban commercial banks to be in line with the Vietnamese market economy.

On 11 June 2006, the government promulgated decree No.141/2006/NĐ-CP on the list of legal capital of credit institutions. Then, the regulation on the grant of licenses for the establishment and operation of joint-stock commercial banks was promulgated by the Decree No.24/2007/QĐ-NHNN, which aimed at increasing the minimum charter capital from 732.70 billion VND to 1000 billion VND. In this way, rural commercial banks are transformed into urban commercial banks.

The transformation of banks was greatly important. It not only made the authorised capital increase but also changed the administration system of each bank to be suitable with the international development trends.

In August, 2007, there were 13 requirements for establishing new banks with an authorised capital of over VND 1000 billion.

Table 1 Joint stock commercial bank after 2007

Unit: VND billions

No.	Joint stock commercial bank	Authorised capital	Located
1	Lien Viet	3,300	HauGiang
2	PPT(TienPhong)	1,000	Ha Noi
3	Van Phong	1,000	KhanhHoa
4	Nang Luong	1,000	Ha Noi
5	Viet Tin	1,680	HCM
6	KinhBac	1,500	BacNinh
7	Dong Duong Thuong Tin Commercial Joint Stock Bank (IDB)	1,000	Ha Noi
8	Viet Nam	1,000	HCM
9	Viet Nam urban development	1,000	Ha Noi
10	Petro	1,000	Ha Noi
11	Foreign trade of Asia	1,000	Ha Noi
12	Dong Duong	1,000	Long An

Source: State bank of Vietnam

The inefficient operation of State Enterprises (SOE) made it more difficult for the economy to develop. Therefore, the equitization was inevitable, especially in the financial crisis in 2008.

During 2007-2013 period, there were 5 big commercial banks in Vietnam: Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade of Viet Nam (Vietcombank), Viet Nam Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Industry and Trade (Vietinbank), Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam, Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (Agribank) and Housing Bank of Mekong Delta (MHB).

Table 2 The operational status of state bank before and after privatization

Billion VND (%)	Year	Total assets	Author-ised capital	Operating cost	ROA (%)	ROE (%)	Bad debt ratio (%)	CAR (%)
Vietinbank	2008	193,590	13,400	4,958	1	17	1.81	7.27
	2015	779,000	49,000	10,72	0.79	10.28	0.9	10.92
BIDV	2011	405,755	12,948	6,652	0.83	13.20	2.96	11.07
	2013	548,386	28,112	7,436	0.78	13.80	2.37	10.23
	2015	857,000	34,187	11,09	0.76	15	1.71	9
Vietcombank	2007	197,363	4,429	1,628	1.44	21.21	NA	12.25
	2013	468,994	23,174	6,244	4.48	7.84	2.73	13.13
	2015	674,395	26,650	8,306	0.85	12.03	2.1	10.91
MHB	2011	47,282	3,062	938	0.17	2.62	2.31	NA
	2012	37,980	2,708	1,210	0.73	9.44	2.99	16
	2014	45,142	3,062	1,116	0.31	3.65	NA	NA

Source: State bank of Vietnam

State-owned commercial banks after equitization had done well at leading the market, became one of the effective physical forces of the government in the implementation of macro regulation policies through financial and money market (For example: BIDV supported post-merger operations of SCB, Ficombank and TinchiaBank and so on).

Generally, after the implementation privatization, it can be seen that the maturity and growth of state-owned commercial banks in general and the banking system in particular.

With credit market share of 70% in Vietnam, the state-owned commercial banks contributed important capital to the industrial and economic sector development.

Diversification commercial services are to meet the requirements of customers. The effectiveness of business and finance in the Vietnamese banking system was clear.

Total assets and authorized capital increased clearly after privatization (except for MHB), the biggest asset and capital belonged to Vietinbank and the smallest ones belonged to MHB.

Besides, the operating costs also increased. Vietinbank had the highest cost and MHB had the lowest one. Generally, ROA and ROE increased after privatization. Vietinbank had the highest ROA and MB had the lowest one. The highest ROE belonged to BIDV and the lowest one belonged to Vietcombank.

In 2013, MHB was the bank with the highest profit again. This was the main point making the difference among top 5 joint stock banks. By the absolute-value comparator, although the profit in 2013 was slightly lower than in 2012, MHB still had the highest pre-tax profit margin (3013,9 billion VND).

Also, after privatization, Vietcombank, Vietinbank and MHB actively promoted the financial capability, expanded the scale of operation, implemented solution gradually to become large sized banks in the area.

Nowadays, Vietcombank and Vietinbank are two commercial banks with the biggest authorized capital, total assets have increased by several times compared to 2001.

After privatization, the growth rate of those two banks has always been high in all sectors. The key finance indicators achieved high level, ensured that the safety indicators were maintained at Vietnam's and international standards, the bad debt rate dropped to lowest level in the entire system.

They were also two banks that always kept the main role in meeting the capital needs and financial services businesses in order to maintain and expand production, contributed actively to the results of the Socio-Economic Development plan of the government. According to Bizlive, there were 12 banks that had planned for increasing capital in 2015. If they fill the norm, the total of charter capital of 21 banks would be 244.957 billion VND, increased of 16.3% compared to the results at the end of 2014.

a. Vietnam's bank restructuring

After the state bank announced the bank's restructuring list, some of them had successfully self-restructuring like Tienphongbank and Navibank.

Table 3. Banks self-restructured successfully

Bank	Date	Finance	Human resources	Technology	Product	Cost	Operating model	Corporate governance
Navibank	6/2013	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
TienPhongBank	7/2012	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Daitin bank	9/2012	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Source: State bank of Vietnam

Almost all the banks had a complete restructuring plan including finance, technology, human resources, technology, and corporate governance and operating model.

Table 4: Result after banking restructuring

Billion VND	Year	Assets	Authorized capital	Operating expense	Employees	ROA (%)	ROE (%)	CAR (%)	Bad debt rate (%)
Navibank	2012	21,585	3,010	650	1583	0.02	0.10	19.09	5.64
	2013	29,074	3,010	618	1593	0.08	0.75	16.03	6.07
	2015	48,230	3,010	655,2	2100	0.02	0.2	NA	2.13
Tien Phong Bank	2010	20,889	3,000	197	716	0.77	8.08	18	0.02
	2013	32,088	5,550	423	1183	0.10	10.89	19.81	1.97
	2015	76,220	5,550	794,7		0.88	12.44	>9	0.97
Total	Before	42,474	6,010	847	2299	0.40	4.09	18.55	2.83
	After	61,162	8,560	1,041	2776	0.09	5.82	17.92	4.02
Dai Tin bank	2011	27,130	3,000	312	1,376	0.60	5.10	NA	NA
	2013	28,000	3,000	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Source: State bank of Vietnam, financial statement of commercial banks

TienPhong Commercial Joint Stock Bank was one of the typical banks that did self-restructuring. It overcame a number of difficulties to develop stability during the financial crisis in 2010. With bad debt up to 6%, the administration system was ineffective, the liquidity got trouble, the authorized capital was under permitted level, Tienphong was one of the most ineffective banks. In 2012, Tienphong Bank decided to join the bank restructuring. With the support of the shareholders and Doji Corporation with effective growth strategy, the authorized capital of TienPhong bank had increased, from 3,000 VND (2012) to 1,550 trillion VND (3/2014). Its profit after tax reached 381 billion VND. The total of mobilization reached 10,785 billion VND, the business loan reached 8,617 billion VND. NPL ratio declined by half compared with 2012, ROE = 10.89%, CAR=19.81%.

Total assets after restructuring increased by 50% compared to the prior restructuring and this was demonstrated in TienPhongbank in specific (In 2010, it was 20,889 billion VND before restructuring and after that process, it was 32,088 billion VND in 2013). In 2014, the net interest income reached 979,171 billion VND, which was 1.6-fold increase compared with the prior year. ROE was much higher than before. In Navibank, it increased from 0.1% (2012) to 0.75% (2013) and in Tienphongbank, it grew from 8.08% (2010) to 10.89% (2013).

In Navibank, the rate of ROA increased to 0.08% (2012), which is four times compare to that in 2013 (0,02%). In 2016, Navibank set the profit target at about 300 billion VND. CAR rose 1.81% from 18% (2012) to 19.81% (2013)) in TienPhongBank.

In general, after self-restructuring, the number of employees grew in all bank and the rate increased to over 65.22% compared to before (There were 716 people before self-restructuring in 2010 and 1,183 people after that progress in 2013)

In December 2013, VNCB boosted its authorized capital to 7,500 billion VND. Up until May 2014, two top leaders of the VNCB - Pham Cong Danh, the former Chairman and Phan Thanh Mai, the former general director were arrested, the financial data of this bank had not been updated since the name was changed (The new name is Dai Tin Bank).

b. M&A Domestic banks sections

In recent years, M & A has been a common measure that many banks choose to restructure them. Currently, Vietnam has 12 cases of mergers and acquisitions banking.

Table 5: M&A of Vietnamese banks

	Date	Before restructure	Measure	After restructure	Abbr.
1	15/12/2011	De Nhat joint-stock commercial bank Tin Nghia joint-stock commercial bank SaiGon joint-stock commercial bank	Merger	SaiGon joint-stock commercial bank	SCB
2	28/08/2012	Ha Noi joint-stock commercial bank SaiGon Ha Noi joint-stock commercial bank	Merger	SaiGon Ha Noi joint-stock commercial bank	SHB
3	3/10/2013	Laoviet bank Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment	Acquisition	Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and development	BIDV
4	9/2013	Ho Chi Minh Joint Stock Commercial Bank for development Dai A joint-stock commercial bank	Merger	Ho Chi Minh Joint Stock Commercial Bank for development	HDB

5	26/03/2014	southern joint-stock commercial bank SaiGonThuong Tin joint-stock commercial bank	Merger	SaiGonThuong Tin joint-stock commercial bank	SCB
6	19/04/2014	Me Kong joint-stock commercial bank for development Maritime bank	Merger	Maritime bank	MSB
7	23/04/2013	Maybank An Binh joint-stock commercial bank International finance corporation	Merger	An Binh joint-stock	ABB
8	01/09/2012	Lien Viet joint-stock commercial bank Viet post corporation	Merger	Lien Viet post bank	LPB
9	9/2012	ThienThanh corporation Dai Tin bank	Acquisition	Vietnamese construction joint-stock commercial bank	VNCB
10	5/2015	Me Kong joint-stock commercial bank for development Maritime bank	Merger	Maritime bank	Maritime Bank
11	5/2015	Me Kong housing bank Bank for Investment	Merger	Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and development	BIDV
12	5/2015	PG Bank VietinBank	Merger	Joint Stock Commercial Bank for industry and trade	CTG

Source: State bank of Vietnam, financial statement of commercial banks

The majority of banks had been restructured by transforming model and on-going capital increase. It could be said that after the merger of the authorized capital, the assets of these banks intensified greatly. The details are as below:

Table 6: Result after banking after the merger of the authorized capital

		Total of asset	Authorized capital	Operating expenses	Empl -oyees	ROA (%)	ROE (%)	CAR (%)	Bad debt rate (%)
SCB	2010	60,183	4,185	588	2,075	0.83	10.50	10.32	11.40
Ficom bank		7,649	2,000	60	418	2.29	6.69	43.54	2.20
TinNghia bank		46,414	3,399	288	1,044	1.24	5.00	NA	0.83
Sum		114,246	9,584	937	3,537	1.45	7.40	26.93	4.81
SCB	2013	181,018	12,295	1,807	3,233	0.03	0.35	9.95	1.63
	2015	311,513	14,294	2,618	NA	0.04	0.54	NA	
HBB	2011	41,285	4,050	516	1,864	0.78	7.80	16.46	4.42
SHB		70,992	4,815	1,126	2,840	1.75	22.50	13.37	2.23
Sum		112,277	8,865	1,642	4,704	1.27	15.15	14.92	3.33
SHB	2013	143,626	8,866	1,860	5,002	0.70	9.66	12.38	4.06
	2015	274,765	9,486	2,035	5,957	0.43	7.47	11.33	
BIDV	2012	484,785	23,012	6,765	18,546	0.83	12.90	NA	2.90
	2013	548,386	28,112	7,436	18,231	0.78	13.80	10.23	2.37
	2015	850,748	31,481		23,687	0.8	14.4	9	
DaiA Bank	2012	18,079	3,100	456	1,434	1.36	7.30	22.25	4.40
HDB		52,783	5,000	797	2,227	0.90	9.12	14.10	4.33
Sum		70,862	8,100	1,253	3,661	1.13	8.21	18.18	4.37
HDB	2013	86,227	8,100	1,118	4,953	0.57	5.66	12.20	3.67
	2014	99,525	8,100	1,820	6,242	0.51	5.46	NA	
ABB	2012	46013	4,200	1095	2,766	0.24	2.50	NA	NA
	2013	57,791	4,800	1,052	2,590	0.37	3.47	NA	4.80
	2015	67,382	4,800	1,186	3,023	0.14	1.56	NA	
LVB	2011	56,132	6,010	940	1,972	2.14	18.26	NA	2.14
LPB	2013	79,594	6,460	1,191	1,974	1.74	7.73	NA	2.48

	2015	107,587	6,460	1,563	3,849	0.34	6.47		
DaiTin Bank	2011	27,130	3,000	312	1,376	0.60	5.10	NA	1.65
VNCB	2013	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Sourth Bank	2013	77,558	4,000	376	3,276	0.02	0.42	NA	3.70
STB		160,159	12,425	4,098	10,710	1.38	14.30	10.22	1.44
	2015								
MDB	2013	6,437	3,750	568	1,082	0.86	1.61	NA	2.65
MSB		102,802	8,000	1,636	3,536	0.39	4.30	10.56	2.71

Source: State bank of Vietnam, financial statement of commercial banks

After the bank mergers, although BIDV had the largest total assets and authorized capital, the increasing rates of possession ratio and authorized capital in SCB was highest in 2013. It indicated that SCB had the most effective restructured route with its authorized capital growth and slightly high assets (54.5% and 28.3%). Meanwhile, the operation indicators plummeted (ROA and ROE decreased by 95% and 98%) prior to merging. The reasons for this reduction could be the sharply rise of the total operating expenses of SCB (92.89% compared with before merging, reached 1,802 billion) and the reduction in staff. Moreover, the overspending on cost contingency budget of SCB was another cause. Besides, SCB’s NPL ratio also had multiplied changes. Especially, it fell from 11.4% in 2011 to 1.63% in 2013. It was obvious that SCB decided to make a trade-off between focusing on financial capacity, improving credit quality, reducing credit risk loans and offsetting plummeted performance extents. Up to now, it could be said that SCB, one of the joint-stock commercial banks, has the most successful restructuring ever in Viet Nam. Coming from the merger of the three weakest banks, SCB is now in the top five of leading joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam, after the Military Commercial Joint Stock Banks.

Figure 1: Result after the merger of the authorized capital

Source: State bank of Vietnam, financial statement of commercial banks

It can be seen that although ABB had the smallest total assets and authorized capital after the merger (figure 3.1), the profit indicators of operation are the highest (Figure 3.1) (ROA rose of 54.2% corresponds to 0,37% and ROE rose by 38.8% relative to 2.5% in 2013). The total operating costs and the number of staffs dropped significantly (4% and 6.4%). Hence, the rising operational efficiency of ABB can be derived from the reduction of unnecessary costs and excessive staff.

On the other hand, two banks (SHB and HDB) still did not have many outstanding achievements. While the ROE, ROA decreased and NPL ratio increased, the authorized capital by the end of 2013 was equal to this one after the merger. After the merger, SHB might be the least effective banks. With the total assets rose 30% compared to the time of the merger, the authorized capital almost remained unchanged (0.01%). The ROA and ROE came down significantly (44.7% and 36.2%), and the bad debt rate was the highest in the bank system. This is due to the fact that SHB had to endure a “huge” bad debt and the serious loss of liquidity statement from Habubank that made SCB’s profit drop sharply (ROA fell from 1.75% to 0.27% and ROE decreased from 22.5% down to 9.66% in 2013). However, the signal of SCB’s recovery could be seen by the downturn of NPL ratio (from 8.8% in 2012 to 4.08% in 2013). Although the current operational status of the SCB has been difficult, with this rate, SCB will soon overcome its weak condition.

Figure 2: Result after banking consolidation and merger in 2015
 Source: State bank of Vietnam, financial statement of commercial banks

Even though three mergers had no specific statistics but after the process of consolidation and merger, the banking systems in general and the individual banks in particular still get more benefit than loss. After overcoming severe consequences, the economy will achieve banking system stability. With the policy of the state bank, the financial indicators of the bank like ROE and ROA reduced significantly in 2013 prior to merger. The state banks strictly stepped up inspections, control of bad debts. The disposal of bad loans was executed by issuing Document 8986/NHNN-TTGSNH on loan classification, provisioning and using provisions for bad debts. Deducting bad debts too much made the gains fall considerably in combination with debt sold to VACM fund management company. Within the next five years, these financial indicators do not tend to increase until the bad debt is resolved.

The year of 2015 was considered as the last year of enforcing scheme 254 (Scheme: Restructuring the system of credit institutions during the period 2011-2015). One of objectives of this scheme, according to the State Bank Governor, was to developing the systems of credit institutions in the direction of modern multi-functional, safe operation, firm efficient with diversified structures, ownerships and sizes ... Striving to the end of 2015 to form at least 1- 2 commercial banks with the scale and qualifications on a par with other banks in the region.

3. Establishment of Asset Management Company

In difficult times like the present, solving the weakness of the banking system should be top priority and the establishment of an asset management company is an inevitable phenomenon.

In Vietnam, Vietnam Asset Management Company (VAMC) was established under Decision No. 1459 / QD-NHNN dated 06/27/2013 by the Governor of the State Bank of Vietnam as 100% Stated owned of the capital. VAMC is a special tool to contribute to resolve NPLs, reduce risks for credit institutions and enterprises, promote reasonable credit growth to the economy and is one office of the Vietnamese bank as 100% Stated owned of the capital. This company was subjected to state's management, inspected and supervised directly by State Bank of Vietnam, operating with the authorized capital of 500 billion VND and the principle of self-financing; not for profits, publicity and transparency; minimizing the risks and costs of bad debt.

Table 7: Banking bond and bad debt statement in 2013 and 2014

Banks	Special bond		Bad debt	
	Signing date	value (billion VND)	Bad debt	Bad debt rate (%)
Agribank	1/10/2013	1,723	33519	6.54
PGBank	4/10/2013	170	1197	9.1
SCB	4/10/2013	548		>3
SHB	4/10/2013	75	5289	9.04
PNB	11/10/2013	155	1189	2.77
SCB	11/10/2013	1,192		>3
Total		3,863		

Source: State bank of Vietnam, financial statement of commercial banks

On 31 December 2013, VAMC bought 38,900 billion VND worth of original debt from 35 credit institutions with around 32,400 billion VND worth of special bonds issued. Vietnam Asset Management Companies (VAMC) has purchased 2,534 billion VND bad debt of the Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development of Vietnam (Agribank) (end of 2013), represented 6.5% of the entire banking system.

VAMC officially purchased 39,000 billion VND worth of original debt from 01/10/2013 to 12/31/2013, exceeded the plan of 35,000 billion. After purchased, VAMC implemented synthesis, classified and drawn up a list of debts to offer to the domestic and international markets in the near future.

In the first quarter of 2014, VAMC bought 3,929 billion VND worth of original debt from the credit institutions. It was the total value of 169 debts that this company purchased from 10 credit institutions in Vietnam including BIDV, SCB, SHB, Viettinbank, Sacombank, Lienvietpost bank, VP bank, Techcombank, VIB and Vietcombank in the first 3 months of 2014, including a state-owned credit institution.

By the end of May 2014, VAMC bought NPLs worth about 6,075 billion VND from 13 credit institutions, raising the total bad debts it had purchased from credit institutions to 47,401 billion VND.

In June 2014, VAMC conducted an auction of 390 billion VND worth of debts and authorized credit institutions to deal with about 500 billion bad debts.

In the market report dated 08.01.2015, Ho Chi Minh City Securities Corporation (HSC) said that VAMC had handled 7.7% of NPLs bought to date.

4. Loosen room for foreign investors

Understanding the importance of foreign investors, the government has issued a remuneration policy with the aim to attract foreign investment for helping disadvantaged businesses as:

According to decree No. 69/2007/ND-CP, the maximum shareholding a foreign strategic investor and its/his/her affiliated person may have is 15%.

The decree also states that the percentage of shareholding that a foreign investor have may not exceed 5% of the charter capital of a credit institution in Vietnam.

At the proposal of the State bank of Vietnam, a foreign strategic investor or its/his/her affiliated person to hold share exceeding 15% but not exceeding 20% of the charter capital of a Vietnamese credit institution.

The ratio of shareholding of a foreign investor and its affiliated person will not be exceeding 20% of the charter capital of a credit institution in Vietnam.

In January 2014, the government issued a new decree deciding to allow foreign investor to hold shares up to 30% of the charter capital of a commercial bank in Vietnam. The total shareholding of the foreign investors in a Vietnamese non-bank credit institution is under public companies and listed companies' law.

In special cases, the Prime Minister would decide on the total shareholding percentage for foreign organization, foreign strategic investors in a weak and restructured joint-stock credit institution which might exceed the limits, specific for each situation. The above regulations include the capital that the investors authorize to purchase for foreign organizations and individual investors.

In June 2015, additional decrees prescribed the ratio of foreign ownership in Vietnam stock market. According to them, the ratio of foreign ownership in public companies as follows:

If international treaties in which Vietnam is a member have provisions on the foreign ownership ratio, it shall be in conformity with such international treaties.

With respect to a public company conducting business activities which are subject to a foreign ownership ratio by investment laws, the foreign ownership ratio in such public company shall be in conformity with the applicable laws.

With respect to a public company conducting business activities which are conditional for foreign investors, and in which there is no specific provision on the foreign ownership ratio, the foreign ownership ratio will be at maximum 49%.

With respect to public company conducting different business activities in which foreign ownership ratios have been provided differently, the proportion of foreign ownership shall not exceed the minimum ratio specific in relation to the business activities which such company is conducting, unless otherwise stipulated in any applicable international treaty.

For public companies, which are not in the specific above, the rate of the foreign ownership is unlimited, unless otherwise provided in the charter of such company.

The decree stipulated for SOEs privatization implementation, with respect to public offers of securities, the rate of the foreign ownership in accordance with the law on privatization. In case law on privatization has no provisions, this rate will comply with the corresponding provisions.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study describes the overall picture of the restructuring process in Vietnam's early stages. The study offers an analysis of bank restructuring in a small and transitional economy. From 2011 to 2015, the state bank and commercial banks have implemented many restructuring methods such as Self-restructuring, M&A Domestic banks sections, Establishment of Asset Management Company and Loosen room for foreign investors.

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